

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A476

10 September 1996

OXICOA — TACIA

ADDENDUM

The correct dates for each of the flights
are as follows:-

475	9	September	1996
476	10	September	1996
477	11	September	1996
478	13	September	1996
479	16	September	1996
480	17	September	1996
481	19	September	1996

TACIA OXICOA AUG-SEPT 96 Flight Summary

Prepared by: Andrew Kaye and Hannah Richer

[1] A475 9/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 1 2 hr 40 min

A short test flight for the chemistry instrumentation was carried out. The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). After initial concerns about the NO background, the NO_x instrument was found to operate satisfactorily on the two available channels (NO and NO₂).

An anticyclone centred to the west of the UK provided possible TACIA type weather. However, delays, due to incomplete airworthiness certification, meant that there was insufficient time to search for plumes from the UK. However, a small local plume was encountered in the Bristol Channel (51.36N, 4.12E).

Data from this flight could possibly be used to validate emission data from South Wales.

[2] A476 10/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 2 4 hr 30 min

Instruments performed as in the previous test flight: The ozone, peroxide and formaldehyde instruments performed well. PAN was found to be below the detection limit of the GC's. The CO instrument did not work well (showing a large variability in background measurements). The NO background had improved and the NO_x instrument was generally found to operate well on the two channels (NO and NO₂). However, on reaching maximum altitude difficulties were encountered on controlling the flow rate in the NO₂ channel.

A persistent anticyclone centred to the west of the UK again provided TACIA type conditions. However, delays, due to instrument requirements, meant that there was limited time to search for plumes from the UK. However, cross wind runs were carried out at an interval of approximately 60 miles along the SW coast. Trajectory analysis is to be carried out to determine whether the same air mass was sampled twice. However, no particularly notable plumes could be distinguished from the ozone, carbon monoxide and formaldehyde data. However, useful background information was obtained.

[3] A477 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 00 min

The presence of an occluded frontal system over Norway/North Sea facilitated the study of three different airmasses.

Profiles were successfully flown on both sides of the warm front, but there was not sufficient time to travel to the northern edge of the cold frontal surface. However the lowest levels of the second stack may have been north of the front.

Ozone, formaldehyde and PAN instruments worked well, but the CO background problem was not corrected and the NO_x NO₂ channel flow problem had not been resolved.

[4] A478 11/9/96 TACIA TEST FLIGHT 3 2 hr 56 min

Thursday 12 September was used to install the NO_y converters and rectify the CO instrument. The CO work was successful. However the NO_y converters took longer than expected to complete. This resulted in a delayed take off.

Although primarily a TACIA instrument test flight the opportunity was taken to characterise the Arctic Maritime air mass over the North Sea. This effectively completed the work started on A477.

The chemistry kit performed as well as could be expected given the reduced warm up times available. The ozone pump switched off unexpectedly during the flight which caused a loss of data until the problem was identified.

[5] A479 11/9/96 TACIA 5 hr 40 min

There was a high pressure centred over the North Sea on this day which gave rise to continental outflow in the south-west approaches.

A very successful trial of the TACIA flying pattern, with two stacks being flown to sample continental air. A double inversion (875 and 950 mbar) was identified effectively capping pollutants and isolating them from the ocean surface sinks. Elevated levels of aerosol, CO (170 ppb), NO (40 ppt), NO₂ (400 ppt) and O₃ (65 ppb) were noted in this layer. Another interesting parcel of air was also sampled at higher altitudes (6 - 8 km). This air parcel was characterised by high levels of CO and aerosol. All the chemistry instrumentation performed well and the flight will provide a valuable contribution to the TACIA experiment.

[6] A480 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight 6 hr 04 min

An anticyclone was centred to the north of the North Sea, such that continental plumes from northern Europe were reaching southern England across the North Sea. The same anticyclone was investigated during flight A479, at which time the high was centred over the UK.

The aim of this flight was to characterise air parcels within the anticyclone: both air parcels with recent continental influence and those with mainly marine back trajectories were studied. The highest pollutant concentrations of the campaign were measured during this flight in the boundary layer near Boscombe Down and in the marine boundary layer in the southern North Sea.

The marine boundary layer was distinct from the rest of the troposphere by a low level inversion. A slightly higher inversion was also apparent in profiles carried out north of 54 N. Interestingly, the seemingly typical vertical structure was not found in the southern North Sea: only the marine inversion was present.

A plume was encountered in the marine boundary layer at the first sampling region and elevated NO_x, NO_y and CO were observed with a corresponding decrease in ozone, indicating recent anthropogenic inputs. Profiles throughout the lowest 6000 ft of the atmosphere, whilst travelling northward, indicated some chemically aged parcels of air with elevated ozone, CO and NO_y. Haze layers were also visible. However, most of the air was generally clean. Further North, haze layers were less frequent, but layers with elevated ozone were still apparent. Elevated CO with a corresponding decrease in ozone indicated some recent pollution in the marine boundary layer at 57.2 N and 0.8 E.

All the chemistry instruments performed well during the flight. In particular, the peroxide measurements were found to show similar features to the calculated peroxide. Pitch, roll and yaw manoeuvres were carried out in order to test the NO_x inlets: preliminary results indicated that there were no large effects.

[7] A481 11/9/96 OXICOA Airmass characterization Flight/NO_x test 6 hr 16 min

An attempt was made at an airmass characterization flight. However, within an hour of take off, the peroxide and CO instruments had failed completely and the NO_x was only functioning at 50%. After consultation with the instrument operators it was decided that useful tests could still be carried with the operational NO_x channels and the flight plan was changed to a NO_x test flight. Several NILU and MRF bottles were also filled for analysis of hydrocarbons and possibly CO.

However, it is interesting to note that, at one point, air of stratospheric origin was encountered: we were frustrated by the lack of a complete suite of instruments. Recently polluted air and air which was chemically aged, as indicated by ratios of NO_x/NO_y and ozone, were both sampled. Useful data on emissions from north eastern Europe may have been gained.

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 476

DATE: 10/9/196

Take off: 1120

Landing: 1550

Aircraft Scientist : H. RICHARD

Flight Leader : I. POUL

Others 2D : D. ALTHAM

PARA/OS : J. KENT

CO : S. WESSLER / C. GERRICK

NOX : K. DUNN / S. BARUTTE

BOTTUS : D. RIDDEMAN

PERSONAL : D. BANDY

FORWARD CHIEF : L. CARDINAS

: A. KAYE + P. MONKS

Captain : M. POUSE

Co-pilot : C. O'BRIEN

Navigator : J. CANNING

Engineer : N. NEWTON

Loadmaster : K. QUICK

Trials Instructions WAF-13

TACIA

Operating area : S.W. APPROACHES

General synoptic situation

TIME :

111939

T/O Proximal Dam

112908(10) - 113702(12)	PROFILE P1	3000' → 10000'		
113945(14) - 115542(15)	RUN 1	FL80	285°	
115542(15) - 115825(16)	PROFILE P2	FL80 → FL110		
115825(16) - 120821(17)	RUN 2	FL110	295°	
120916(18) - 122118(20)	PROFILE P3	FL110 → 50'		(029-1)
122240(21) - 123235(22)	RUN 3	2000'	240°	
123434(23) - 124432(24)	RUN 4	FL50	110°	
124700(25) - 125656(26)	RUN 5	FL90	300°	
12585(27) - 130741(28)	RUN 6	FL110		
130741(28) - 132403(29)	PROFILE P4	FL110 → 50'		1027
132631(31) - 134606(32)	RUN 7	2000'	295°	
134723(33) - 135040(34)	PROFILE P5	2000' → FL50		
135040(34) - 140039(35)	RUN 8	FL50	120°	
140039(35) - 140240(36)	PROFILE P6	FL50 → FL70		
140358(37) - 141350(38)	RUN 9	FL70	305°	
141504(39) - 141801(40)	PROFILE P7	FL70 → FL100		
141701(40) - 142757(41)	RUN 10	FL100	120°	
142841(42) - 143146(43)	PROFILE P8	FL100 → FL130		
143146(43) - 144643(46)	RUN 11	FL130	040°	
144643(46) - 150522(48)	PROFILE P9	FL130 → FL270		
150522(48) - 151524(49)	RUN 12	FL270	105°	
151651(50) - 15448(51)	PROFILE P10	FL270 → 50'		

154716

LAND Proximal Dam

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log. ✓ Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
	✓ Flight Leader pre-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight check form ✓ Flight Leader in-flight log ✓ Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
1	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log <i>ECAC</i>
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log ✓ 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log ✓ Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
	✓ Instrument status forms ✓ RTD prints ✓ Raw data plots ✓ Weather charts Satellite pictures ✓ GPS track

A476 10-SEP-96 11:29:08-15:41:48GMT

A476 10-SEP-96 Height time series

Sortie Brief: TACIA - Instrument Test Flight

Sortie Objective: Plumes from the UK and/or Northern Europe will be sought at progressively greater distances from land.

Operational Area: SW Approaches/Brest Peninsula. Travelling across wind for horizontal transects and with the wind between sampling areas, crossing flight regions to be discussed with navigator.

Weather conditions: Anticyclone centred over UK is preferable for TACIA experiment. Avoid areas of cloud and precipitation where possible.

Flight Pattern:

1. Depart Boscombe Down and transit at FL¹³⁰150 to sampling area.
2. Execute a ^{stepped} profile descent from approx. FL250 to FL050 at 1000ft/min. Continue descent at 500ft/min to minimum safe altitude. ^{Max altitude (maintain 10 min)} STEPS AT FL090, FL070 x 5000ft (10 minutes each).
3. Execute horizontal runs perpendicular to wind direction (1) at levels determined by aircraft scientist (approx. 40 minutes).
4. Transit with the wind for approx. 50-100nm.
5. Profile from approx. FL100 to minimum safe altitude and repeat [3,4].
6. Repeat as time allows
7. Transit to Boscombe Down, maintaining constant altitude for 15 minutes.

Other requirements: Constant pressurisation on horizontal runs.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Project: 11 Date: 19/9/96

Aircraft Scientist:

Flight No: A476

Page 1 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
					Latitude	Longitude		
11:20:00	9			276	51.1	-2.3	ASCEND -1. 2000 FT AFTER TAKE OFF JUST IN CLOUD (STRATUS)	
11:21:08	10	P1	300ft	276	51.17	-2.49	PROFILE 1 1000ft/min. 2000ft → FL130	
11:30:00			4000ft	276	51.17	-2.5	ABOVE BROKEN CU AT 4000ft	
			6600ft				BACK INTO CLOUD 6000ft → QUICKLY OUT OF THIN LAYER (STCU)	
11:34:00			7200ft	277	51.18	-2.87	STRONG TEMP INVERSION 6800ft → 7200ft	
				277A	51.18	-3.07	CIRUS ABOVE 478 COMPLEX SKY THIN STRATUS BELOW 8/8 WITH SOME CUMULUS & STRATOCUMULUS	
11:37:00	13			274	51.18	-3.16	LEAKS IN WET CHEM FORCED TO DESCEND. TO FLOSO	
11:39:45	14	Run1	8500ft		51.20	-3.43	OVER SEA LESS CU 1/8 THIN STRATUS 8/8	
11:52:37				ORBIT	51.18	-4.54	ORBIT RIGHT TO FINISH NOFY CALIBRATION (STILL PART OF RUN)	
11:55:42	15	P2		279	51.20	-4.63	OZONE INCREASING INCREASING ON CLIMB 1000ft/min UNMAX AT 11:57	
11:58:50	16	Run2		290	51.21	-4.86	NOW IN RUN OUT OF O3 MAX 1!	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: M RICHARD

Project: TACIA TEST Date: 10/9/96
 Flight No: A476 Page 2 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
12:05:17		R2			285	51.29	-5.	SMALL O ₃ PEAK DETECTED ON RUN CO PEAKS ALSO NOTED (SHARP).	
12:08:21	17	R3			93	51.3	-5.6	END RUN 2 BEGIN PROFILE 1000ft/min O ₃ 62 PPB 905Kft	
								O ₃ FALLING ON DESCENT	
12:21:28	20	P			304	51.28	-4.74	DOWN TO 50 ft PROFILE UP TO 2000 FT	
12:22:14	21	R3	2000ft			51.29	-4.80	IN THE BOTTOM OF THIN SHEET OF STRATUS.	
12:32:39	22				286	51.28	-5.57	END OF RUN 3	
12:34:34	23	R4	5500ft		104	51.37	-5.49	OZONE 45-50 PPB, CO INCREASED	
12:44:32	24	P	8200ft			51.25	-4.80	PROFILE TO FLO90 (END OF RUN 4)	
12:47:00	25	R5	9000ft		296	51.26	-4.91	O ₃ UP TO APPROX 55 PPB → 60 PPB (MAX) CO & O ₃ POSS ANTICORRELATION.	
12:50:26	26							DOWN POINT & O ₃ DEFINATE ANTICORRELATION ON ALL THREE RUNS.	
12:56:56	26	P						END OF RUN 5. STEPHANE NOMINAL READING CA. 100 PPT	
12:58:51	27	R6	11,000ft		183	51.36	-5.76	CO, O ₃ REMAINING SIMILAR TO FLO90	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H RICHES

Project: THIN
TEST
Flight No: A476

Date: 10/9/96

Page 3 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:06:00		R6	FL110		182	50.93	-5.80	O ₃ RISING TO MAX OF 75 PPB	
13:07:41	28	R4			182	50.81	-5.81	END OF RUN 6	
13:09:24	29		8200ft		184	50.68	-5.83	CO INCREASING & O ₃ DECREASE PROFILE 1000ft/min to 2 nd SAMPLING AREA	
13:14:00			4700ft		183	50.4	-5.8	EARLIER STRONG INVERSION IS LESS APPARENT AND IS LOWER	
13:15:15			4000ft			50.40	-5.86	ENTERING STRATUS STRONG INVERSION	
13:24:03	30		50ft		128	49.87	-5.96	END PROFILE 4 SEA STATE 3	
13:26:31	31	R7	2000ft		290	49.94	-6.00	RUN 7 CO + O ₃ RISING (PAST SCILLY ISLES)	
13:34:57						50.09	-6.71	SHIPS OBSERVED OZONE DECREASE MIN 33 PPB	
13:41:07						50.19	-7.14	RUN EXTENDED FOR 5MINS AFTER NO _x CAL	
								O ₃ QUITE VARIABLE ON THIS RUN SOME ANTICORRELATION WITH DEWPOINT	
								BUT SOME CHANGES IN CONCENTRATION ARE UNRELATED	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H RICHAR

Project: TACIA TEST
 Date: 10/9/96
 Flight No: A476 Page 4 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (cg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
13:46:06	32	R7	2000ft			50.28	-7.59	END OF RUN PROFILE 1000ft/MIN to 5000 5000ft	
13:47:23	33	P				50.31	-7.52	OZONE INCREASING, DEWPOINT DECREASING (ANTICORRELATED)	
13:50:00	34	R8	5000ft					O ₃	
13:55:51					103	50.15	-6.92	O ₃ DECREASE TO 28 PPB. (DOWN AS LOW AS 25 PPB) ANTICORRELATED WITH H ₂ O ₂	
14:00:39	35	P			102	50.07	-6.57	END OF RUN 8 O ₃ INCREASING ON ASCENT	
14:03	36	R8			102				
14:07:58	37	R9	7000ft		296	50.08	-6.42	START RUN 9 O ₃ ca. 50 PPB H ₂ O ₂ 1.75 PPB	
								O ₃ SHOWING A STRONG ANTICORRELATION WITH DEWPOINT DEWPOINT	
14:13:56	38	R9			294	50.26	-7.17	VERY LITTLE CU BELOW WITH HAZE (POSS. THIN STRATUS). END OF RUN	
14:15:04	39	P7						START OF PROFILE	
14:18:01	40	R10	10000 ' FT		115			AGAIN LOW O ₃ . BUT RISING TO A MAX OF 62 PPB, AGAIN ANTICORRELATED WITH	
14:27:57		R10				49.96	-6.11	DEWPOINT END OF RUN	

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: H RICHES

Project: TACIA TEST Date: 10/9/96
 Flight No: A476 Page 5 of 6

GMT	Event Mark	Run No.	Height	Pres/Rad	INS Heading	Omega Pos'n		Other Info. (eg. clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)	Photo No.
						Latitude	Longitude		
14:28:21	42	P8				50.02 -6.05	PROFILE O ₃ INCREASING TO 62 PPB		
14:31:46	43	R11	FL130		34	50.13 -5.94	HAZE NOTED IN DISTANCE SOME BROKEN CUMULOS BELOW CLEAR ABOVE		
							SOME CO & O ₃ CORRELATION SEEN ON RUN - DIFFICULT TO SEE DUE TO CO		
14:46:53	46	R11				50.89 -5.11	INSTRUMENT PROBLEMS. APPARENTLY, NO _x & O ₃ CORRELATION END RUN		
14:46:53	48	P9			33	50.89 -5.11	END RUN 11 START P9, to Max ALTITUDE		
14:50:00			FL170			51.09 -4.8	CO APPARENTLY INCREASING WITH O ₃ DECREASE		
14:57:45							O ₃ REMAINING CONSTANT AT 40 PPB FROM 14:51:00 CORRESPONDING CHANGE EQUIVALENT POTTEMP & DEW POINT		
15:01:30			FL250		93	51.1 -3.7	O ₃ RISING		
15:05:22	48	R12	FL270		95	51.10 -3.33	O ₃ 75 PPB STRATOSPHERIC INFLUENCE * SPIKES IN NO & NO ₂ (CANNOT GIVE NO ₂ CONC. DUE FLOW PROBLEMS). ATTEMPT TO CORRECT THIS ON DESCENT. *TEMP. INVERSION NOT MARKED		
15:15:29	49					51.10 -2.25	PROFILE END RUN		

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A476 Date: 10/9/66 User: H. RICHER
Interactive by: I. RUIZ
Date: 12/9/66

Renav

DONE BY KALMAN FILTERING

TWC

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : ~~Profile~~ / Whole flight / ~~Other~~

a = - 0.3875E+1
b = + 0.2584E-2
c = + 0.5752E-6

LWC

LITTLE CLOUD PLAIN INTO EXCEPT AT EITHER END
OF FLIGHT

Heimann / Barnes

NO CALS

FWKS

UNABLE TO WATCH SIBUT PATH TO GF.

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: A476 Date: 10/9/96 A/S Name: H. RICHIE

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required? 3
YES NO for
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period INDEF.
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project DAEIA
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? INDEF.
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? ... ?
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A476

Date: 10/9/96

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
081	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx	0568
	REF -	7	2855	✓		Approx	2858
	AOSS	19	1713		F/S TORQUE 0/S 2-0	2047 st.	and level
	AOA	18	3691		F/S TORQUE 0/S 3-0	2047 st.	and level
	RD HT	37	0000	✓		As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	3890	100	✓	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	4008	100	154 ✓		
	A/S	9	0082	✓		As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1245	390			
	UP2S	82	1150	200			
	UIRS	83	0390		JNO ₂		
	UP1Z	84	0151	✓		Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	0145	✓		Approx	0149
	UIRZ	86	0302		JNO ₂	Approx	2061
	UP1T	87	2528	} 17		As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2536			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000		JNO ₂	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0198	20			
	LP2S	92	0207	-20			
	LIRS	93	0035		JNO ₂		
	LP1Z	94	0151	✓		Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95	0160	✓		Approx	0146
	LIRZ	96	0033		JNO ₂	Approx	2050
	LP1T	97	2479	17		As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2337	21		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0000		JNO ₂	As IAT	
	J/W	42	0996	0 ✓		As Indicated	0000
	NEPH	47	X				
	HYGR	58	2768	8.5			
	HYCC	59	0713	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	6045	} In-flight Protection??		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	6045				
	DTF	10	3924	14			
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	3482	13		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	X				
	CCN	140				less than 4095 if ON	
	TWCD	70	2615	✓		0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	0721	✓		0640-1860	< min
	O3	100	0052				
	O3P	106	2023			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	1584				
	HEIM	141	2653				
	PEFL	142	2394				

HCO 150 1153
ORGP 0151 0009
H202 0152 0025
00 0151 0022

PLGT 180 1291
PTRN 187 1306
PELO 188 0279

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	476	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0085	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0342	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	7			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				X			
	LATC	160	Dec	4094			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4034			Longitude

51°09'90" = 51.165
001 44.68 = 1.745

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 0 FT

51 09.83 = 51.164
001 44.63 = 1.744

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
0854	TWCD	70	2606	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1078	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	0220	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2296		BIT W?	2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2245	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2072	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2130	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1025	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4089			4095	
	EV1V	170	2245				
	EV2V	171	2043				
	NPWR	172	3427				
	EVIC	173	3468				
	EV2C	174	2968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear		
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red	OFF / ON	Large/Small
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon JN2		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear		
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red	OFF / ON	
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon JN2		

Flight Leader's ~~File~~/In-Flight Check List

CHEK
for auto selection

Flight No: A476 Date: 10/9/96

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GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2855	✓			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	1796	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	1007	✓	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	4095	✓	> 5000		As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	2801	8900	9000		As Altimeter
	CABP	14	4000	1000	(1005?)		
	A/S	9	1342	185	✓		As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	1440	450			
	UP2S	82	1279	230			
	UIRS	83	0550		JNO ₂		
	UP1Z	84	0153	✓			Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0147	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0647		JNO ₂		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	2656	} 9			As IAT
	UP2T	88	2673				As IAT
	UIRT	89	0220		JNO ₂		As IAT
	LP1S	91	0245	100			
	LP2S	92	0573	100			
	LIRS	93	0177	100	JNO ₂		
	LP1Z	94	0150	✓			Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0161	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0176		JNO ₂		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	2674	} 9			As IAT
	LP2T	98	2641				As IAT
	LIRT	99	0222		JNO ₂		As IAT
	J/W	42	1138	0.0			As Indicated 0000
	NEPH	47					
	HYGR	58	1840	-20			
	HYCC	59	0758	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	1587				DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0902				
	DTF	10	2553	8			
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	2305	8			same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	X				
	CCN	140					less than 4095 if ON
	TWCD	70	1444				0000-4094
	TSAM	72	1383				0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	0169				
	O3P	106	2023				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
1150	O3RG	113	2071				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	476	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	122	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	445	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	21	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
				 			
	LATC	160	Dec	583	SI		Latitude
	LONG	161	Dec	4081	-5		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	2258	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2561	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1370	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2793	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2250	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	0755	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2609	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1020	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4015			4095	
	EV1V	170	3475				
	EV2V	171	3138				
	NPWR	172	2670				
	EVIC	173	4016				
	EV2C	174	3998				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 476.....

Date 10/9/96.....

Page 1..... of 2.....

Video Tape
No. A476 #1
Ends 1435
FFC / DEC / REC

	GPS	INU
Lat	51° 04.40N	51° 04.88N
Long	01° 44.68W	001 44.68W
Time	090142	
Status	ALL 5's	GC ALLAN

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
074813			DATA ON						
105425			SAT INU TO NAV						
111939			T/O BOSKOWSKI DOWN						
			START P1 ↑						
112907	10	3000'		280	180				
113226	11	START	VIDEO TAPE RECORDING COUNT = 0000						
			HTR / END P1						
115702	12	10000'		280					
			START RUN 1						
115845	14	FL10		285	185	3.5	-25		
			END RUN 1 / START PROFILE 2 ↑						
115542	15	FL10		285	180				
			END PROFILE 2 / START RUN 2						
115825	16	FL110		295	180	0.7	-4		
			END RUN 2						
120824	17	FL110		290	180	0.3	-22	OFF	
			START PROFILE 3 ✓						
120816	18	FL110		100	180			2490 (19)	500'/WIN 75c
			END / START P3						
122415	20	50'	1029	100	180			SS=3	2000 5000 9000
			START RUN 3						
122240	21	2000		290	185	9	7	OFF	
			END RUN 3						
123255	22	2000							

Video Tape	
No.	A476#1
Ends	1435
FFC / DFC / DFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51.31 N	51.32 N 51.32 N
Long	-5.14 W	-5.18 W
Time	1250	1250
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/na
HORACE recording to disc	y/na
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/na

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr		Wind/ Sea st.
123434	23	FL500	1013	110	180	2	0.5	OFF		
124432	24	FL500								
126700	25	FL900		300	180	2.9	-31	OFF		
125056	26	FL900								
125851	27	FL1100			190	180	0.4	-31	OFF	
130741	28	FL1100								
131345	29	SWITCH TO		500	140					
132403	29	50'	1027	190						SS=3
132651	31	2000'	1027	245	180	8.6	5.3	OFF		
134600	32	2000'	1027							
134723	33	2000'	1027							5000
										7000
135040	34	FL500	1013	120	175	4.6	-2	OFF		10000
140051	35	FL500	1013	110	180					
140240	36	FL800								

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 476..... Date 10/9/96..... Page 2 of 2.....

Video Tape	
No. A476#1	Ends 1433
FFC / DEC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	50°08.16N	50°08.88N
Long	06°44.05W	06°48.61W
Time	1406	1409
Status	5	NAV

DRS recording to HORACE	y / no
HORACE recording to disc	y / no
SATCOM sending pos. reports	y / no

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
140358	37	FL70							
141356	38	FL70							
141504	39	FL70							
141801	40	FL100	1013	120					
142757	41	FL100							
142841	42	FL100							
143146	43	FL130							
144643	46	FL130							
143538	44	END	VIDEO	A476#1	COUNT = 6149				
143638	45	START	VIDEO	A476#2	COUNT = 6000				
145640	47	FL215							
150322	48	FL270	1013	105	180	-34	-44	OFF	
151524	49	FL270							
151651	50	FL270							

Video Tape	
No.	A476#2
Ends	1736
FFC / DFC / RF	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	y/n
HORACE recording to disc	y/n
SATCOM sending pos reports	y/n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
			END P10			(OVER BORCADE)			
154148	SI	50'							
154710			LAND BORCADE						
								GPS POS ON PAN	
								SI-09-83	
155210			DATA OFF					00144634 @ 15512	
1552			VIDEO STOPPED						

VIDEO TAPE LOG

Flight No A 476

Project TACIA

Date 10/9/96

Tape No A476#1 User H. Richter

Retention Period INDEF

GMT	Tape Counter	Camera Position	Remarks
113326	0030	FFC	START RECORDING EVM = 11
143538	0149	FFC	STOP RECORDING/END OF TAPE EVM =

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Ver. 2.3a
TIME +1

Flight No. A476 Date: 10/9/96 Operator: DWA

Page 1 of

GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	CONC/CC	MAX SIZ.	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZ.	CONC/1.	MAX SIZ.	
										1. PROFILE 1
113945	43		✓			✓				RUN 1 START
1147.53	39	1.0	—			—				(RUN 1 END → START PROFILE P2 ↓)
1155.42	36	1.09	—			—				↓
1158.25	26	1.09	—			—				END OF P1 START OF RUN 2
1203	30	1.08	—			—				↓
120821	43	1.09	—			—				END OF RUN 2
120916	74	1.11	—			—				PROFILE 3
121007	195	1.12	—			—				9900'
121132	63	1.1	—			—				8300
121340	465	1.1	—			—				6500
121500	415	1.11	.02	3.5		—				5000
121611	420	1.1	.02	3.5		—				4000
121805	826	1.11	.26	9.5		—				2000
121901	1156	1.11	.5	6.5		—				1000
122002	850	1.12	.1	3.5		—				500
122118	973	1.11	.26	2.5		—				end of PROFILE P3
122240	576	1.11	.5	6.5		—				start of RUN 3 2000'
122440	708	1.1	.0	4.0		—				
122650	695	1.1	.05	3.5	2	—				
122950	716	1.11	.25	3.5	2	—				
1232.35	535	1.10	.26	3.5	2	—				end of RUN 3
123434	500	1.11	—	—	—	—				start of RUN 4 5000'
123814	360	1.11	—	—	—	—				
124031	320	1.11								
124310	340	0.5	.02	6.5	—					
124432	350	0.8	—	—	—					end of RUN 4

* DRS TIME

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. 4476 Date: 10/9/96 Operator: DWA Page 2 of 4

GMT	PCASP		FSSP		2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC	MAX SIZE	CONC/1.	MAX SIZE	
124700	45	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	START OF RUN 5 9000'
125100	45	.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
125545	60	.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
125656	95	.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Run 5 start of Run 6 11000'
125851	40	.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
130254	40	.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
130741	87	.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Run 6. START of P4
131005	38	.03	-	-	-	-	-	-	8500'
131136	43	.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	7200'
131342	280	.45	-	-	-	-	-	-	5000'
131512	440	2.7	170	27	3	-	-	-	4200'
131708	610	1.3	0.05	35	1.5	-	-	-	3000'
131823	290	.6	0.05	65	3.7	-	-	-	2000'
132115	480	.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	1200'
132403	910	1.7	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Profile P4
132631	410	0.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	start of Run 7 2000'
133138	360	0.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	
133732	450	0.1	.05	9.5	1.7	-	-	-	
134150	660	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	
134606	430	0.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Run 7 @ 2000'
134723	400	1.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	start of Profile P5.
134913	300	0.5	-	0.3	6.5	-	-	-	" 4000'
135040	62	0.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Profile P5 Start of Run 8. 5000'
135503	117	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
135824	19	0.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	
140039	46	.35	-	-	-	-	-	-	end of Run 8 Start of Profile P6

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A476 Date: 10/9/66

Operator: Dwt

Page 3 of 4

GMT *	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/L	MAX SIZE	
140214	41	0.35	-	-		-	-			End of PROFILE P6 FL 70.
140358	44	0.45	-	-		-	-			Start of Run 9 FL 70
140807	36	0.6	-	-		-	-			Run 9 FL 70
141215	41	1.7	-	-		-	-			Run 9 FL 70.
141356	38	.45	-	-		-	-			End of Run 9 start of
141504	41	.35	-	-		-	-			Start of profile P7 FL 70 ↑
141801	45	.6	-	-		-	-			End of profile P7 Start of Run 10 FL 70
142002	37	.6	-	-		-	-			Run 10 FL 10
142757	23	.3	-	-		-	-			End of Run 10.
142841	52	.3	-	-		-	-			Start of P8
143146	24	.45	-	-		-	-			End of P8 Start of Run 11 FL 130
144105	43	.45	-	-		-	-			Run 11 FL 130.
144643	25	.35	-	-		-	-			End of Run 11 Start of PROFILE P9
145241	95	.35	-	-		-	-			19000'
145705	45	.35	-	-		-	-			22000'
150005	6.1	.15	-	-		-	-			24000'
150342	10.7	.27	-	-		-	-			26000'
150522	15.7	.27	-	-		-	-			End of Profile Start of Run 12 FL 270
151524	24	.6	-	-		-	-			End of Run 12.
151651	12	.35	-	-		-	-			Start of Profile P10
152546	32	.6	-	-		-	-			17500
152751	170	.35	-	-		-	-			15500
153110	37	.45	-	-		-	-			12200
153310	140	.6	-	-		-	-			11000
153440	83	.45	-	-		-	-			8300
153537	365	.8	-	-		-	-			6500

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. A476 Date: 10/9/96

Operator: DWA

Page 4 of 4

GMT*	PCASP		FSSP			2D-C		2D-P		REMARKS
	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	CONC/CC	MAX SIZE	R _{eff}	CONCL	MAX SIZE	CONC/1L	MAX SIZE	
153720	DS	.8	0.15	6.5	2.5	—		—		PROFILE P10. 4500'
153900	5A0	.45	0.04	8.5	2.5	—				
153945	2332	1.7	0.18	12.5	2.3					
154037	2300	1.7	.2	35	3					800'
154148	2300	0.8	.2	2.5	2.1					End of profile
154221										STOP.

* DRS TIME

DATE 10 SEP 96 TI MRF 1

NAV CANADA

AIRFIELD BD

AIRFIELD BD

R/W 05 W/V 020 TEMP 15 QNH OFF

R/W 05 W/V 020 TEMP 15 QNH 1023 OFF 1000

WX :L 18K 2

WX B.M

ATC CL 1 3000 6507 54

ATC CL

T/O TIME 1220

LAND TIME 1650

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT/LONG	RUN
1129 ⁰⁹	277	28	192	178	185	031/16	3000		N 51087 W 02269	P1
37 ⁰⁰							F110		N 51100 W 03098	P1
39 ⁴⁵	270	46	209	182	208	004/8	F80		N 51105 W 03254	R1
55 ⁴⁰	274	18	203	180	207	345/19	F80		N 51160 W 04399	- P2
58 ²⁵		28	212	180	214	013/16	F10		N 51119 W 04547	R2
08 ²¹									N 51185 W 05492	-
1209 ¹⁶	098	45	212	180	210	014/22	350		N 51202 W 05481	R3
							50		N 51149 W 04480	-
22 ⁴⁰			193	185	185	021/9	2000		N 51162 W 0448 W	R3
									N 51226 W 05369	-
34 ³⁰	103	182	205	180	195	054/17	F50		N 51203 W 05326	R4
44 ³²							-		N 51111 W 04462	-
47 ⁰⁰	296	28	203	178	207	357/18	F90		N 51140 W 04521	R5
56 ⁵⁶									N 51268 W 05425	-
58 ⁵¹	182	20	222	177	212	006/15	F110		N 51218 W 05461	R6
1307 ⁴¹	024	18	214	180	210	001/14			N 50474 W 05486	- P4
249							50		N 49512 W 05586	-
263	292	30	195	180	182	049/16	2000	1023	N 49546 W 05590	R7
46 ⁰¹									N 5052 W 07344	-
47 ³⁸	109	65	173	173	174	059/18	F50		N 50766 W 07317	P5
50 ⁴⁰	109	35	189	182	194	060/12	F50		N 50126 W 07183	R8
1400 ²⁴	103	45	199	181	200	050/10			N 50023 W 06388	P6
02 ⁴⁸							F70		N 50013 W 06223	-

TIME	HDG	DR	G/S	IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT/FL	QNH/PR	LAT / LONG	RUN
1403 ⁵⁸	294	4P	204	180	200	028/16	F70		N 50026 W 06214	R9
13 ⁵⁶									N 50146 W 07122	—
15 ⁰⁴	114	2S	196	173	198	034/11	F100		N 50139 W 07039	R7
18 ⁰¹	113	2S	217	181	216	018/11	F100		N 51110 W 06556	R10
27 ⁵⁸									N 49556 W 06056	—
28 ⁴¹	034	1S	201	175	211	026/12	F120		N 49562 W 06034	R8
31 ⁴⁰	035	1P	123	186	216	020/9	F130		N 50057 W 05531	R11
40 ⁴⁵	034	1S	214	182	232	031/14	F270		N 50494 W 05063	R01
1525 ²⁰	012	SS	210	180	265	010/25	F220		N 51052 W 03250	R12
15 ²⁶									N 51041 W 02143	—
16 ⁵¹	077	2P	237	188	271	500/23	→		N 51002 W 02169	R12
41 ⁴⁰									BOSCAFE TITESTELA	—

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: *A476*

DATE: *10/9/96*

MRF *13*

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	X		
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	✓	✓	
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
LOWER CLEAR	✓	✓	
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	✓	✓	<i>JNO₂</i>
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	✓	X	
CLOUD PHYSICS	✓	✓	
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	X		

A476

10-SEP-96

12:29:33

021 02

51.36

-5.37 FR P

HDG deg T 286.	SPR mb 954.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 189.	TAT C 9.4	DEW C 6.9	WIND deg m/s 014/6
----------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

A476

10-SEP-96

12:26:27

021 02

51.32

-5.12 FR P

HDG degT 286.	SPR mb 954.	PHGT kft 1.6	TAS knots 184.	TAT C 9.5	DEW C 6.6	WIND deg m/s 020/7
---------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

PRESS -GT 500.07 m 00 MP 100.00 PPb 000NE MP 10.01 PPb
 0.00 00.00 000.07 1000.00 1000.00 1000.00 1000.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

A476 10-SEP-96 12:25:21 021 02 51.31 -5.03 FR P

HDG degT 286.	SPR mb 955.	PHGT kft 1.6	TAS knots 186.	TAT C 9.5	DEW C 6.7	WIND deg m/s 027/7
---------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	--------------------------

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A476

10-SEP-96

13:31:48

031 Ω

50.02

-6.41 FR P

HDG deg T 293.	SPR mb 953.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 187.	TAT C 8.6	DEW C 4.1	WIND deg m/s 056/12	
----------------------	-------------------	--------------------	----------------------	-----------------	-----------------	---------------------------	--

5000.00 4000.00 3000.00 2000.00 1000.00 0.00

0.00 1.00 2.00 3.00 4.00 5.00

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
-------------	-----------	-----------	---	---	---	------------	---

A476

10-SEP-96

13:30:36

031 02

50.00

-6.32 FR P

HDG deg T 293.	SPR mb 953.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 187.	TAT C 8.5	DEW C 4.5	WIND deg m/s 058/11	
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SPR - 953.00 PHGT - 1.70 TAS - 187.00 TAT - 8.50 DEW - 4.50 WIND - 058/11

A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A476 10-SEP-96 13:29:00 031 02 49.97 -6.19 FR P

HDG deg 293.	SPR mb 953.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 189.	TAT C 8.4	DEW C 5.6	WIND deg m/s 051/11
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0.00 5000.00 10000.00 15000.00 20000.00 25000.00 30000.00 35000.00 40000.00 45000.00 50000.00

0.00 5000.00 10000.00 15000.00 20000.00 25000.00 30000.00 35000.00 40000.00 45000.00 50000.00

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A476 10-SEP-96 13:27:57 031 00 49.96 -6.11 FR P

HDG degT 292.	SPR mb 953.	PHGT kft 1.7	TAS knots 188.	TAT C 8.4	DEW C 5.6	WIND deg m/s 048/10
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM			VIDEO		

A476 10-SEP-96 13:41:33 031 0 50.20 -7.19 FR P

HDG deg	SPR mb	PHGT kft	TAS knts	TAT C	DEW C	WIND deg m/s
292.	953.	1.7	186.	8.5	6.3	057/11

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A476 10-SEP-96 15:12:30 048 51.04 -2.60 FR P

HDG deg T 78.	SPR mb 345.	PHGT kft 26.9	TAS knots 278.	TAT C -37.3	DEW C -45.5	WIND deg m/s 014/10	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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A476 10-SEP-96 15:08:30 048 51.08 -3.07 FR P

HDG degT 92.	SPR mb 346.	PHGT kft 26.9	TAS knts 271.	TAT C -36.7	DEW C -47.1	WIND deg m/s 015/12
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A476

10-SEP-96

15:06:54

048

51.10

-3.25 FR P

HDG deg T 94.	SPR mb 345.	PHGT kft 26.9	TAS knots 281.	TAT C -36.6	DEW C -47.0	WIND deg m/s 015/12	
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A SELECT	B CHEM	C ZOOM	D	E	F	G VIDEO	H
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M410

10-DEC-70

10.00.00

041 --

01.11

0.40 IN 1

HDG degT 93.	SPR mb 348.	PHGT kft 26.8	TAS knots 257.	TAT C -36.1	DEW C -45.7	WIND deg m/s 015/12
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A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
SELECT	CHEM	ZOOM				VIDEO	

A476	10-SEP-96	14:33:27	043	50.21	-5.85	FC	P								
H06	deg T	32.	SFR	620.	PHGT	13.0	TAS	223.	TAT	-2.7	DEW	-28.8	WIND	deg m/s	029 / 5

OZONE MR 61.31 TWC DEWP^c -26.82

SELECT	PARMS	FREQ	ZOOM		VIDEO	HELP	
A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H

T+0

500-1000MB
500MB

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

0
GMAIN

00Z TUES 10/ 9/96 VT 00Z TUES 10/ 9/96

PHEA50 EGRR 0000Z
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 05-39.27
F02
CHART 13

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 21

** TOTAL PAGE: 001 **

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_2 PAGE. 001

10 SEP '96 15:33

A476.TXT

From 0Z 7/ 9/1996 to 12Z 10/ 9/1996

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 25-Oct-1996 16:00

A476 10-SEP-96

P1 3000ft-FL100(112908-113702) + P2 FL80-FL110(115542-115824)

A476 10-SEP-96

P3 FL110-50ft(120916-122118) + Stack1 50ft-FL110(122118-125851)

A476 10-SEP-96

P4 FL110-50ft(130741-132403) + Stack2 50ft-FL130(132403-143146)

A476 10-SEP-96

P9 FL130-FL270(144643-150522) + P10 FL270-50ft(151651-154148)

A476 10-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL100 From 112908-113702 Plotted 11-04-1996 11:39

A476 10-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL100 From 112908-113702 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:39

A476 10-SEP-96 P1 3000ft-FL100 From 112908-113702 Plotted 11-04-1996 11:39

A476 10-SEP-96 R1 FL80 From 113945-115542 Plotted 11-01-1996 11:43

A476 10-SEP-96 R1 FL80 From 113945-115542 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:43

A476 10-SEP-96 R1 FL80 From 113945-115542 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:43

A476 10-SEP-96 R1 FL80 From 113945-115542 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:43

A476 10-SEP-96 R1 FL80 From 113945-115542 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:43

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 958
Mean 752.636
Standard dev 0.528590
Max value 754.837
Min value 751.365

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 958
Mean 276.258
Standard dev 0.430462
Max value 277.213
Min value 274.975

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 958
Mean 253.738
Standard dev 4.12385
Max value 262.694
Min value 245.730

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 958
Mean 50.7284
Standard dev 2.04471
Max value 54.1118
Min value 44.5407

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 958
Mean 36.7050
Standard dev 9.15576
Max value 70.0501
Min value 15.0019

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 958
Mean 2.373564e-04
Standard dev 2.312676e-03
Max value 2.342930e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 958
Mean 2438.23
Standard dev 5.59547
Max value 2451.70
Min value 2414.94

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 958
Mean 51.0752
Standard dev 2.12904
Max value 51.2164
Min value 4.127947e-03

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 958
Mean -4.09831
Standard dev 0.743478
Max value 14.9963
Min value -4.67130

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 958
Mean -8.26697
Standard dev 16.3122
Max value 495.143
Min value -10.6963

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 958
Mean 1.26052
Standard dev 2.68426
Max value 76.2745
Min value -1.39905

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 958
Mean 0.802567
Standard dev 14.3881
Max value 445.460
Min value -0.530403

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 958
Mean 8.94964
Standard dev 0.985584
Max value 10.7431
Min value 5.05542

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 351.331

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 958
Mean 106.445
Standard dev 2.11074
Max value 111.804
Min value 102.859

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 270.478

A476 10-SEP-96 P2 FL80-FL110 From 115542-115824 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:44

A476 10-SEP-96 P2 FL80-FL110 From 115542-115824 Plotted 11-06-1996 11:44

A476 10-SEP-96 P2 FL80-FL110 From 115542-115824 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:44

A476 10-SEP-96 R2 FL110 From 115825-120821 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 11:46

A476 10-SEP-96 R2 FL110 From 115825-120821 Plotted 11-04-1996 11:46

A476 10-SEP-96 R2 FL110 From 115825-120821 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:46

A476 10-SEP-96 R2 FL110 From 115825-120821 Plotted 11-02-1996 11:46

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 670.423
 Standard dev 0.290349
 Max value 671.973
 Min value 669.905

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 273.650
 Standard dev 0.238987
 Max value 274.265
 Min value 273.258

DEW POINT (DEG K)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 250.790
 Standard dev 2.39976
 Max value 255.806
 Min value 243.904

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 55.9945
 Standard dev 4.13587
 Max value 66.7808
 Min value 48.6517

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 50.7015
 Standard dev 18.0895
 Max value 111.152
 Min value 11.0014

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 2.932496e-04
 Standard dev 2.518672e-03
 Max value 2.235456e-02
 Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 3350.12
 Standard dev 3.37597
 Max value 3356.16
 Min value 3332.11

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 51.2525
 Standard dev 3.299998e-02
 Max value 51.3087
 Min value 51.1942

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
 No of obs 597
 Mean -5.34201
 Standard dev 0.270628
 Max value -4.87766
 Min value -5.81098

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 597
 Mean -9.11426
 Standard dev 0.649359
 Max value -7.89771
 Min value -10.2930

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 597
 Mean -1.32216
 Standard dev 0.718632
 Max value 6.250763e-02
 Min value -3.03337

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
 No of obs 597
 Mean -0.302840
 Standard dev 0.593645
 Max value 0.524429
 Min value -1.87393

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 9.23613
 Standard dev 0.670060
 Max value 10.3822
 Min value 8.00712

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
 Mean 8.25404

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
 No of obs 597
 Mean 111.957
 Standard dev 1.31888
 Max value 113.628
 Min value 106.687

HEADING (DEG)
 Mean 281.062

A476 10-SEP-96 P3 FL110-50ft From 120916-122118 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:49

A476 10-SEP-96 P3 FL110-50ft From 120916-122118 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:49

A476 10-SEP-96 P3 FL110-50ft From 120916-122118 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:49

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-01-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack1 50ft-FL110 From 122118-125851 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:56

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 2254
Mean 838.209
Standard dev 98.0485
Max value 1025.65
Min value 670.480

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 2254
Mean 278.222
Standard dev 3.37918
Max value 288.054
Min value 272.357

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 2254
Mean 264.748
Standard dev 16.7509
Max value 283.614
Min value 235.366

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 2254
Mean 49.0084
Standard dev 6.31697
Max value 64.7295
Min value 36.4678

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 2254
Mean 352.540
Standard dev 279.073
Max value 1167.99
Min value 13.0013

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 2254
Mean 4.993108e-02
Standard dev 0.108863
Max value 1.00513
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 2254
Mean 1616.48
Standard dev 956.586
Max value 3349.46
Min value -102.744

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2254
Mean 51.3095
Standard dev 6.479838e-02
Max value 51.4496
Min value 51.1844

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 2254
Mean -5.22397
Standard dev 0.295325
Max value -4.74563
Min value -5.76853

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2254
Mean -6.93696
Standard dev 2.38960
Max value -0.511955
Min value -12.4514

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2254
Mean -3.24860
Standard dev 2.67395
Max value 2.16232
Min value -8.78197

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 2254
Mean -0.343561
Standard dev 0.508918
Max value 1.31446
Min value -2.11798

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 2254
Mean 8.31541
Standard dev 1.54411
Max value 12.5300
Min value 2.95912

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 25.0939

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 2254
Mean 100.128
Standard dev 5.94003
Max value 111.585
Min value 86.1849

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 280.691

A476 10-SEP-96 R6 FL110 From 125851-130741 Plotted 11-01-1996 11:59

A476 10-SEP-96 R6 FL110 From 125851-130741 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:59

A476 10-SEP-96 R6 FL110 From 125851-130741 Plotted 11-06-1996 11:59

A476 10-SEP-96 R6 FL110 From 125851-130741 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:59

A476 10-SEP-96 R6 FL110 From 125851-130741 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 11:59

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 531
Mean 670.438
Standard dev 0.227125
Max value 670.927
Min value 669.734

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 531
Mean 273.787
Standard dev 0.183483
Max value 274.250
Min value 273.367

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 531
Mean 248.236
Standard dev 3.39796
Max value 253.267
Min value 239.411

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 531
Mean 60.2927
Standard dev 4.91549
Max value 78.9081
Min value 51.5892

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 531
Mean 62.6530
Standard dev 31.2232
Max value 185.793
Min value 22.0050

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 531
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 531
Mean 3349.95
Standard dev 2.64115
Max value 3358.14
Min value 3344.27

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 531
Mean 51.0811
Standard dev 0.164319
Max value 51.3639
Min value 50.7983

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 531
Mean -5.79125
Standard dev 1.252650e-02
Max value -5.76853
Min value -5.81186

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 531
Mean -6.71472
Standard dev 0.778374
Max value -4.82864
Min value -8.42527

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 531
Mean -0.200557
Standard dev 0.582517
Max value 1.54897
Min value -1.55903

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 531
Mean -0.221588
Standard dev 0.486593
Max value 0.431236
Min value -1.54476

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 531
Mean 6.74345
Standard dev 0.773360
Max value 8.42540
Min value 4.88451

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 1.71082

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 531
Mean 111.910
Standard dev 2.03153
Max value 116.557
Min value 108.467

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 182.759

A476 10-SEP-96 P4 FL110-50ft From 130741-132403 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:03

A476 10-SEP-96 P4 FL110-50ft From 130741-132403 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:03

A476 10-SEP-96 P4 FL110-50ft From 130741-132403 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:03

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:14

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-0ct-1996 12:14

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-01-1996 12:15

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:15

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-04-1996 12:15

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-06-1996 12:15

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:15

A476 10-SEP-96 Stack2 50ft-FL130 From 132403-143146 *Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:15*

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 4064
Mean 837.165
Standard dev 103.889
Max value 1024.87
Min value 622.687

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 4064
Mean 278.440
Standard dev 3.12903
Max value 287.576
Min value 271.243

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 4064
Mean 268.033
Standard dev 10.7429
Max value 281.628
Min value 241.341

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 4064
Mean 45.2487
Standard dev 9.52263
Max value 75.6277
Min value 24.5682

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 4064
Mean 201.025
Standard dev 206.898
Max value 835.559
Min value 7.00068

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 4064
Mean 3.830036e-02
Standard dev 8.530042e-02
Max value 0.518486
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 4064
Mean 1633.01
Standard dev 1023.85
Max value 3922.03
Min value -96.2514

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 4064
Mean 50.0977
Standard dev 0.104215
Max value 50.2819
Min value 49.8406

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 4064
Mean -6.73018
Standard dev 0.448010
Max value -5.90387
Min value -7.57687

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4064
Mean -5.36560
Standard dev 1.44320
Max value -7.880315e-03
Min value -8.41249

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4064
Mean -5.36600
Standard dev 2.63465
Max value 0.150528
Min value -10.4195

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 4064
Mean -0.157593
Standard dev 0.454988
Max value 1.65915
Min value -1.70667

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 4064
Mean 7.79051
Standard dev 2.43208
Max value 12.9483
Min value 3.14607

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 45.0021

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 4064
Mean 101.772
Standard dev 5.90551
Max value 115.410
Min value 89.5974

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 10.8088

A476 10-SEP-96 R11 FL130 From 143146-144643 Plotted 11-01-1996 12:18

A476 10-SEP-96 R11 FL130 From 143146-144643 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:18

A476 10-SEP-96 R11 FL130 From 143146-144643 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:18

A476 10-SEP-96 R11 FL130 From 143146-144643 Plotted 11-02-1996 12:18

A476 10-SEP-96 R11 FL130 From 143146-144643 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:18

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 898
Mean 621.254
Standard dev 0.573142
Max value 622.687
Min value 618.135

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 898
Mean 270.723
Standard dev 0.254926
Max value 271.435
Min value 270.072

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 898
Mean 245.097
Standard dev 3.06000
Max value 252.034
Min value 239.595

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 898
Mean 59.0449
Standard dev 4.19513
Max value 68.8181
Min value 50.0798

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 898
Mean 38.5691
Standard dev 11.9920
Max value 77.0701
Min value 9.00088

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 898
Mean 6.958652e-05
Standard dev 1.202681e-03
Max value 2.118892e-02
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 898
Mean 3939.73
Standard dev 7.09722
Max value 3978.39
Min value 3922.03

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 898
Mean 50.4590
Standard dev 0.210879
Max value 50.8221
Min value 50.0910

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 898
Mean -5.51161
Standard dev 0.227961
Max value -5.11296
Min value -5.90387

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 898
Mean -5.27629
Standard dev 1.07512
Max value -2.94270
Min value -7.25590

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 898
Mean -1.58820
Standard dev 0.398398
Max value -0.517960
Min value -2.84774

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 898
Mean -0.244836
Standard dev 0.422576
Max value 0.930504
Min value -1.34177

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 898
Mean 5.53565
Standard dev 1.01610
Max value 7.35826
Min value 3.58332

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 16.7522

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 898
Mean 115.255
Standard dev 1.77732
Max value 119.187
Min value 111.182

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 34.6390

A476 10-SEP-96 P9 FL130-FL270 From 144643-150522 Plotted 11-04-1996 12:22

A476 10-SEP-96 P9 FL130-FL270 From 144643-150522 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:22

A476 10-SEP-96 P9 FL130-FL270 From 144643-150522 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:22

A476 10-SEP-96 R12 FL270 From 150522-151524 Plotted 11-06-1996 12:24

A476 10-SEP-96 R12 FL270 From 150522-151524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:24

A476 10-SEP-96 R12 FL270 From 150522-151524 Plotted 11-06-1996 12:24

A476 10-SEP-96 R12 FL270 From 150522-151524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:24

A476 10-SEP-96 R12 FL270 From 150522-151524 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:24

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)
No of obs 600
Mean 346.147
Standard dev 0.229613
Max value 347.214
Min value 345.373

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)
No of obs 600
Mean 236.252
Standard dev 0.236934
Max value 236.735
Min value 235.792

DEW POINT (DEG K)
No of obs 600
Mean 227.146
Standard dev 0.739819
Max value 227.942
Min value 225.667

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)
No of obs 600
Mean 71.1548
Standard dev 2.17068
Max value 76.6244
Min value 66.2618

PCASP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 600
Mean 13.9932
Standard dev 5.45956
Max value 37.0180
Min value 2.00006

FSSP CONCENTRATION (CM-3)
No of obs 600
Mean 0.000000
Standard dev 0.000000
Max value 0.000000
Min value 0.000000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)
No of obs 600
Mean 8193.33
Standard dev 4.55998
Max value 8208.71
Min value 8172.16

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 600
Mean 51.0485
Standard dev 1.894907e-02
Max value 51.0886
Min value 51.0191

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)
No of obs 600
Mean -2.84116
Standard dev 0.339288
Max value -2.25951
Min value -3.42947

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -10.5080
Standard dev 0.921649
Max value -8.55133
Min value -12.8470

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -2.61219
Standard dev 0.386590
Max value -1.63037
Min value -3.28156

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean -0.379267
Standard dev 0.446261
Max value 0.826408
Min value -1.76348

WIND SPEED (MS-1)
No of obs 600
Mean 10.8319
Standard dev 0.954137
Max value 13.1729
Min value 8.73133

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)
Mean 13.9602

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)
No of obs 600
Mean 140.699
Standard dev 2.24600
Max value 144.428
Min value 131.778

HEADING (DEG)
Mean 91.5248

A476 10-SEP-96 P10 FL270-50ft From 151651-154148 Plotted 11-Oct-1996 12:26

A476 10-SEP-96 P10 FL270-50ft From 151651-154148 Plotted 11-01-1996 12:26

A476 10-SEP-96 P10 FL270-50ft From 151651-154148 Plotted 11-01-1996 12:26

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems. Pitch and yaw are only displayed for flight A480, where specific manoeuvres were used to test the response of the NO_x inlets.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.
- **FWVS Dew point:** dew point calculated by use of the Lyman- α spectroscopic instrument “the fluorescence water vapour sensor”.

Cloud Physics

- **PCASP:** The Passive Cavity Aerosol Sampling Probe counts number concentrations (number per cm³) of particles in 15 channels spaced pseudo-logarithmically over the diameter range 0.10 μm to 3.00 μm , to provide a particle size distribution over this range.
- **FSSP:** The Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe is used to measure water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47.0 μm diameter (cloud droplets). It has four range settings, each of which is divided into 15 size channels.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **CO:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (raw data). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Stefan Kessler (KFA Julich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb. Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Modelled peroxide:** hydrogen peroxide concentrations as estimated from the concentrations of ozone and water vapour concentrations according to the following algorithm. The model is used in flight and is included in this data summary for individual scientists assessment of the use of algorithms for the purpose of in flight planning. Contact Brian Bandy, Claire Reeves (UEA, Norwich) or Dave Tiddeman (UK Met. Office) for details.

$$H_2O_2 = (k_3 j_4 [O_3] [H_2O]) / (k_5 [M] (j_6 + k_7 + [OH] k_8))$$

where k_3 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + H_2O \rightarrow 2OH$

k_5 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O(^1D) + M \rightarrow O(^3P) + M$

k_8 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $OH + H_2O_2 \rightarrow H_2O + HO_2$

k_7 is the first order loss due to dry deposition. However, as the boundary layer is difficult to define, this term has been ignored for the time being.

j_4 is the rate coefficient for the reaction: $O_3 + h\nu \rightarrow O(^1D) + O_2$

j_6 is the rate coefficient for reaction: $H_2O_2 + h\nu \rightarrow OH + OH$

j_4 , j_6 and $[OH]$, calculated by a 2D model, are dependent upon latitude and time of year.

- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data recorded as bits. NB this instrument has a long time delay *ca.* 12 minutes. Instrument scientist: Laura Cardenas (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters were not recorded on MRF's data recording system and are therefore not available as part of this data summary. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **PAN ECGC's:** Data are not included in this report but will be made available at a later date. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent (UK Met. Office).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section to see when these were filled). Bottle filler: David Tiddeman (UK Met. Office).

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